

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D1.8

Report 2 on actions accomplished for synergies and links
under Tasks 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4

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Executive Summary

This deliverable, *D1.8 “Report 2 on actions accomplished for synergies and links under Tasks 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4”* is part of Tasks 1.2 (*T1.2 “Liaison with Mission Ocean, Seas and Waters Bodies, the Mission Core Network & other Missions”*), 1.3 (*T1.3 “Creation of synergies with European Initiatives and organisations”*) and 1.4 (*T1.4 “Contribution to the EU Agenda for International Ocean Governance, focusing on the UN Decade on Ocean Science for Sustainable Development and the UN Decade of Ecological Restoration (2021-2030)”*).

T1.2 is responsible for collaborating with Mission’s governance bodies and ensured appropriate flexibility of the project activities to accommodate the evolution of the Mission. Engagement with Mission Core Network (TRAMI project) is ensured.

T1.3 aims to connect Ocean and Waters R&I actors to support the Mission's development. It has promoted the Mission Charter through a targeted outreach and social media campaign, encouraging stakeholders to submit actions. The campaign has focused on the benefits of joining the Mission Charter network and guidance on how to contribute. Additionally, T1.3 has delivered a guideline on the implementation of Mission National and/or Regional Hubs and their contributions towards Mission objectives.

T1.4 ensures a close connection between the Mission and the UN Decades (Ocean Decade & Ecological Restoration Decade). T1.4 contributed and exchanged on best practices, funding, monitoring through participation with the *Task force on ocean, seas and inland waters (TransOcean WG)*.

This deliverable gives details the actions taken to build and maintain synergies between Prep4Blue and the Mission Ecosystem on the European and international levels.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
BMAA	BlueMissionAA (Blue Mission Atlantic-Arctic)
BMB	BlueMissionBANOS (Blue Mission Baltic-North Sea)
BMM	BlueMissionMED (Blue Mission Mediterranean)
CSA(s)	Coordination and Support Action project(s)
EcoDaLLi	ECOsysteM-Based Governance with DANube Lighthouse Living Lab for Sustainable Innovation Processes (Blue Mission Danube)
IA(s)	Innovation Action project(s)
LH(s)	Light House(s)
MIP Ocean	Mission Implementation Platform for the Mission “Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 20230”
Mission (Ocean & Waters)	(the) Mission “Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030”
(the) Mission	(the) Mission “Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030”
P4B	Prep4Blue
RIA(s)	Research and Innovation Action project(s)
SBEP	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership
UN Ocean Decade	UN Decade on Ocean Science for Sustainable Development

1 Introduction

Missions are a novel instrument in Horizon Europe, designed to address societal challenges through systemic solutions by 2030. Launched in 2021, via a [European Commission Communication on Missions](#), five thematic missions have been implemented: Restore our Ocean and Waters; Adaptation to Climate Change; Cancer; Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities; and Soil. These EU Missions aim to deliver concrete solutions to some of our greatest societal challenges by 2030, fostering new forms of collaboration, governance and engagement with stakeholders and citizen engagements.

Our focus is the Mission “Restore Our Ocean and Waters” (by 2030) which seeks to create impact by implementing a new role for R&I, developing a portfolio of actions, and establish new forms of governance, collaboration, citizen’s participation. The emphasis on collaboration of the EU Missions is reflected in the three objectives and structure of the Mission “Ocean & Waters”:

1. Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030;
2. Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters, in line with the EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil;
3. Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular, in line with the proposed European Climate Law and the holistic vision enshrined in the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy.

PREP4BLUE serves as the overarching Coordination and Support Action (CSA) for the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean & Waters” (hereafter “the Mission” or “Mission Ocean and Waters”), spanning three years and commencing in June 2022. Its primary objective was to bolster the Research and Innovation (R&I) endeavours of the Mission and facilitate its smooth execution, particularly in its initial phase (2022-2025). Through a series of pilot initiatives conducted at the Mission’s demonstrator sites, also known as ‘Lighthouse’ (LH) sites, PREP4BLUE developed tools, guidelines, processes and methodologies to aid stakeholders across all Mission-funded projects.

WP1’s primary focus has been to align and complement all European Commission (EC), international, national, and regional initiatives to realize the objectives of the Mission. Significant efforts and groundwork have been dedicated to establishing connections between ongoing Mission projects (CSAs, Implementing Actions (IAs), and Research and Innovation Actions (RIAs)), as well as invigorating the Mission ecosystem. Extensive interactions and alignment endeavours have been pursued with LH CSAs, the Mission Secretariat, and the MIP Ocean. Additionally, breakthroughs have been achieved on an international scale through collaborations with various partners involved in initiatives related to the UN Decade on Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, both at strategic and operational levels.

At the European level, Prep4Blue was the representative of the Mission Ocean & Waters with the other Horizon Europe missions (Climate Change, Cities, Soil & Cancer) in the TRAMI project¹. Prep4Blue has been the linking agent between the four Mission LH CSAs

¹ TRAMI project: National Core Network for all Missions, coherence and alignment of programs and resources (<https://www.trami5missions.eu/>)

(BlueMissionAA², BlueMissionMed³, BlueMissionBANOS⁴ and EcoDaLLi⁵), but also between the LH CSAs and the MIP Ocean⁶ as well as with the Mission Secretariat⁷. Prep4Blue helped to align the expectations and efforts of all the CSAs with the MIP Ocean and the Mission Secretariat and it implemented synergies with various European initiatives and organisations and is involved in the whole Mission ecosystem.

At the international level, through partner representatives, Prep4Blue ensures a close connection and alignment of the Mission with both the UN Ocean Decade and the UN Decade of Ecological restoration objectives. This is done through sharing and exchanging on best practices, funding and monitoring in order to create synergies and seek coherence in the areas where the Mission and the UN Decades can be mutually strengthened.

This deliverable, *D1.8 “Report 2 on actions accomplished for synergies and links under Tasks 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4”* is part of Tasks 1.2 (*T1.2 “Liaison with Mission Ocean, Seas and Waters Bodies, the Mission Core Network & other Missions”*), 1.3 (*T1.3 “Creation of synergies with European Initiatives and organisations”*) and 1.4 (*T1.4 “Contribution to the EU Agenda for International Ocean Governance, focusing on the UN Decade on Ocean Science for Sustainable Development and the UN Decade of Ecological Restoration (2021-2030)”*).

This deliverable aims at reporting the accomplishment done in Task 1.2 (see section 2.1), Task 1.3 (see section 2.2) and Task 1.5 (see section 2.3) until the end of the project, at Month 36 (May 2025)

² BlueMissionAA: <https://bluemissionaa.eu/>

³ BlueMissionMed: <https://bluemissionmed.eu/>

⁴ BlueMissionBANOS: <https://bluemissionbanos.eu/>

⁵ EcoDaLLi: <https://ecodalli.eu/>

⁶ MIP Ocean launch: <https://www.technopolis-group.com/new/the-launch-of-mission-restore-our-oceans-and-waters-by-2030-implementation-platform/>

⁷ Mission Secretariat: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters_en#contact

2 Accomplished actions for synergies and links under Tasks 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4

Throughout the second period of the project (M19-M36 / December 2023 – May 2025), Prep4Blue has continued the identification and collaboration with relevant initiatives, projects and organizations. Particular focus with the Mission Ocean and Water bodies; the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP Ocean⁸) and the LH CSAs (BlueMissionAA⁹, BlueMissionMed¹⁰, BlueMissionBANOS¹¹ and EcoDaLLi¹²). The constant coordination of the CSAs has resulted in a CSA Legacy document¹³ (see section 2.1.2) and several working groups (further explained in section 2.1.1). Regular meetings between the Mission LH CSAs and the MIP Ocean have ensured that work is aligned, avoiding duplication of efforts on common objectives while amplifying their collective impact.

Moreover, Prep4Blue by its presence in major European instances such as the Mission Annual Forum, the European Maritime Days and the EurOcean conference, has managed to establish bridges with European Partnerships (*i.e.* EU4Ocean Coalition, Biodiversa+, SPEB, *etc.*) and other EU-funded projects and consortia (CSAs, IAs & RIAs).

Prep4Blue’s coordination team (Coordinator and Project Managers) attended at least 132 synergies meetings between December 2023 and April 2025 (Figure 1). These synergies meetings have been classified in five different categories (Table 2):

- **Mission Ocean and Waters:**
Meetings happening in the general Mission Ocean and Waters ecosystem, excluding the specific LH CSA and MIP Ocean meetings. These “Mission Ocean and Waters” meetings include meetings where Prep4Blue was presented to Mission Stakeholders (Networks, Projects, Conferences, *etc.*)
Example: Mission Annual Forum; SPEB meetings; Blue4All meeting; European Maritime Days; National Mission Ocean Coordination meetings; Associated regions Ocean funding event, etc.
- **LH-MIP Mission Ocean:**
Meetings with the MIP Ocean and one (or all) the LH CSAs.
- **Missions CSAs**
Meetings with one or several of the LH CSAs representatives/partners/consortium. This could also be meetings of the various cross-CSAs working groups.
- **International – UN Ocean Decade:**
Meetings about the UN Ocean Decade or the Ocean at an international level.
Example: Ocean Prediction Decade Collaborative Centre; Preparation of the UNOC conference in 2025; UN Ocean Decade Conference; etc.
- **Other Missions:**
Meetings with the involvement of some of the other Horizon Europe Missions (Climate Change, Soil, Cancer & Cities).

⁸ MIP Ocean: [https://www.technopolis-group.com/new/the-launch-of-mission\[...\]implementation-platform/](https://www.technopolis-group.com/new/the-launch-of-mission[...]implementation-platform/)

⁹ BlueMissionAA: <https://bluemissionaa.eu/>

¹⁰ BlueMissionMed: <https://bluemissionmed.eu/>

¹¹ BlueMissionBANOS: <https://bluemissionbanos.eu/>

¹² EcoDaLLi: <https://ecodalli.eu/>

¹³ CSA Legacy document Version 1.0 : <https://doi.org/10.13155/105135>

Example: TRAMI meetings; Science for policy workshop “Biodiversity and Climate Change”; French National Cross-Mission Meetings (ComOp Recherche – GT Missions), etc.

Table 2. Number of synergy meetings per category type attended by Prep4Blue's Coordination team (Coordinator & Project Managers) from December 2023 to April 2025

Categories of synergy meetings	Number of meetings
International - UN Ocean Decade	21
LH-MIP Mission Ocean	15
Mission CSAs	33
Mission Ocean & Waters	60
Other Missions	3
Total	132

Figure 1. Synergy meetings of Prep4Blue's Coordination Team sorted by Year-Month and category type (Mission Ocean & Waters; LH-MIP Mission Ocean; Mission CSAs; International - UN Ocean Decade; Other Missions) from December 2023 to April 2025.

This represents a total of 132 synergies meetings classified in five category types: Mission Ocean & Waters; LH-MIP Mission Ocean; Mission CSAs; International - UN Ocean Decade; Other Missions.

2.1 Liaison with Mission Ocean, Seas and Water Bodies, the Mission Core Network & Other Missions (Task 1.2)

2.1.1 Mission Ocean and Waters bodies and stakeholders

Prep4Blue has been present in all Mission-related major events and online workshops. These represents 108 synergy meetings (60 “Mission Ocean & Waters” meetings & 33 “Mission CSAs” & 15 “LH-MIP Mission Ocean” meetings) of Prep4Blue’s Coordination team (see Table 2).

These events also allowed Prep4Blue to meet and build links with partners of other projects involved in the Mission, create synergies within the Mission Ecosystem, etc. The links and synergies were more easily built when the meeting was attended in person, however some of the online events also brought in new contacts.

In particular Prep4Blue attended:

- **1st Mission Arena in Gothenburg, Sweden (14-16 November 2023)**

The project was represented by several partners s.Pro, CPMR, JPIO, ERINN Innovation. PREP4BLUE co-organised the session: “Business Models and approaches to support the sustainable blue economy”, which presented preliminary results on policy and business models from Pre4Blue and gathered input from stakeholders.
- **French National “[Horizon Europe Mission ‘Restore Our Ocean and Waters’ Day.](#)” – Organised by French Ministry of Research – Paris, France on 30 January 2024**

The project was represented by the Coordinator (Ifremer). The results of Prep4Blue were shared with the French (future) Mission stakeholders. The French Ministry of Research also signed the Mission Charter in this event.
- **European Ocean (and Waters) Days in March 2024 (Brussels, Belgium)**

The project was represented by several partners including the Coordinator (Ifremer), JPIO, KDM, s.Pro, CNR, CPMR, VLIZ, SDU, Blue Cluster, ERINN Innovation, UCC. This was the first time the Mission Annual Forum was extended to a full week of events: [European Ocean Days](#).

 - **Mission projects matchmaking event - 4th March 2024**
 - **Matchmaking & Networking event - 4th March 2024**

Meetings with Acció - Catalan Government (Karim Hassan Hosny); World Ocean Council (Lisa Simone de Grunt & Paul Holthus); Foundation Philippe Cousteau (Carbajosa Jesus); B2E Blue BioEconomy (Hugo Baroos)
Prep4Blue - EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters" (CINEA interview): https://youtu.be/F7MTotWoZ_4?si=B9G72VU2c9smRSKe

 - **Brittany Delegation to Brussels: meeting with Pierre Karleskind (European Deputy), DG MARE, ...**
 - **2nd annual Mission Ocean Forum – 5th March 2024**

Prep4Blue attended the second Mission Ocean forum in Brussels on the 5th March 2024. The Coordinator had a pitch session, together with the other Mission CSAs (Figure 2), were she presented Prep4Blue’s results in front of an audience of more than a 1000 (both on-site and online): https://youtu.be/Lgx_b7_JIzk?si=aGIM8Mzv_3T7HoMJ&t=16976 (P4B intervention

at 4:42:56). We also had a booth with screen where our results were showcased (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Mission Annual Forum - 5th March 2024 (Brussels, Belgium) : Representatives of DG RTD, DG MARE and the CSA coordinators.

From left to right : Elisabetta Balzi (DG RTD - Head of Unit 'Ocean, Seas and Waters'), Fedra Francocci (CNR – BlueMissionMed), Claudia Pecoraro (DG RTD – Mission Secretariat), Nadja Schlichenmaier (Steinbeis Europa Zentrum – EcoDaLLi), John Bell (DG RTD - Director Healthy Planet), Alberto Terenzi (Submariner – BlueMissionBANOS), Cécile Nys (Ifremer – Prep4Blue), Kestutis Sadauskas (DG MARE - Deputy Director General), Jose Luiz Mountinho (Air Center – BlueMissionAA)

Figure 3. Prep4Blue stand at the Mission Annual Forum 2024 with Prep4Blue representatives.

From left to right: Caecilia Manago (ERINN), Wendy Namisnik (KDM), Barbara Majorano (KDM), Cécile Nys (Ifremer), Jean-Stefan Fritz (KDM)/

During the event the project representatives had the chance to interact with the 400 participants to the event, showcase the objectives and outcomes of Prep4Blue. Several hundred participants tuned in online (Source: [MIP Ocean](#)).

- **Un Ocean Decade in Barcelona, Spain (April 2024)**

The project was represented by several partners including Ifremer, JPIO, KDM, VLIZ, SDU, ERINN Innovation, UCC.

Prep4Blue co-organised 4 side events related to citizen engagement and ocean literacy (See [Deliverable D3.3](#) for more information). Additionally, Prep4Blue organized the Virtual Early Career Ocean Professional (V.ECOP) days, featuring live coverage and social media engagement during the conference.

- **2nd Mission Arena in Riga, Latvia (25-26 April 2024)**

The project was represented by several partners CNR, CPMR, s.Pro, ERINN Innovation. PREP4BLUE played a significant role by financing and organising multiple workshops. Notably, they presented preliminary project results in a session titled “Viable business models for a sustainable blue economy,” focusing on enhancing interactions between research, the public sector, and the business community.

- **3rd Mission Arena in Amsterdam, Netherlands (26-27 November 2024)**

The project was represented by several partners s.Pro, JPIO, SDU, ERINN Innovation, s.Pro, VLIZ, Blue Cluster.

Prep4Blue co-organised two sessions: *Business for BlueGood & WaveLinks, testing the KTSOM*.

- **EMD in Svendborg, Denmark (30-31 May 2024)**

The project was represented by several partners SDU, ERINN Innovation, UCC.

Prep4Blue co-organised, with BlueMissionBANOS, a workshop on *collaborating on citizen engagement*.

- **WIMAFRICA – Cameroon “International Conference of Women in the Maritime and Port Sectors”, 30th May 2024 (online)**

The project was represented by Ifremer (Coordinator).

- **European Ocean (and Waters) Days in March 2025 (Brussels, Belgium)**

The project was represented by several partners including the Coordinator (Ifremer and EuroMarine), JPIO, KDM, s.Pro, CNR, CPMR, VLIZ, SDU, Blue Cluster, ERINN Innovation, UCC.

- **Mission projects matchmaking event - 3rd March 2025**

- **Matchmaking & Networking event - 3rd March 2025**

Ifremer met with BlueSeeds, Centro Tecnológico Naval y del Mar (Marine Technological Center)

- **3rd annual Mission Ocean Forum – 4th March 2024**

During the event the project representatives had the chance to interact with the 1800 participants (both in person and online) to the event.

- **CSA event – 7th March 2025**

During the event, Prep4Blue presented 3 major sections of the CSA Legacy document: Connectivity with the Mission Ecosystem; Barriers and Challenges; Recommendations.

- **Workshops cross-CSAs**

Prep4Blue co-organised with CSAs and IAs, 4 transversal workshops: Business & Regulation (3rd March); Monitoring & KPI (3rd March); WaveLinks (5th March); Knowledge transfer (6th March).

- **EMD in Cork, Ireland (21-23 May 2025)**

Co-organisation of side-events with IAs.

Shared workshop with CSAs on “Mission Ocean-Unlocking Phase 2 - *Scalable Governance*”.

PREP4BLUE and the Lighthouse (LH) Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) have actively worked to identify and foster synergies with relevant initiatives, projects, and organisations. Through ongoing coordination efforts, several joint working groups were established, involving representatives from the LH CSAs and, in some cases, from specific (R)IA (Research and Innovation Actions) projects. These collaborative structures, along with regular meetings between the Mission LH CSAs and MIP Ocean, have helped to align efforts, prevent duplication, and amplify the collective impact of Mission-related activities.

As the overarching CSA for the Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters,” PREP4BLUE played a pivotal role in the “development and piloting” phase (2021–2025), serving as a central connector among the four Mission LH CSAs (BlueMissionAA, BlueMissionMed, BlueMissionBANOS, and EcoDaLLi), MIP Ocean, and the Mission Secretariat. Its role has been essential in harmonising expectations and aligning strategic and operational priorities across the different Mission support structures.

Coordination dynamics in the early phase of PREP4BLUE were shaped by the project's strategic positioning ahead of the Lighthouse (LH) CSAs and the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP). This sequencing, foreseen in the work plan, aimed to allow PREP4BLUE to generate early recommendations

that could inform the LHs. However, some uncertainties—such as the late integration of the Black Sea LH and limited initial clarity around the structure and role of the MIP—meant that interactions during the first year sometimes progressed cautiously and adaptively. Despite these evolving conditions, coordination with the LHs, MIP, and the European Commission was gradually established and strengthened over time. Since March 2024, coordination has significantly intensified, particularly through monthly meetings between MIP and the CSAs. These meetings have become essential for aligning workstreams, synchronising outputs, and ensuring effective communication across all parties. In practice, the experimental nature of the Mission Ocean and its Lighthouses revealed that coordination needs were greater than initially anticipated. As CSA coordinators required more structured support, PREP4BLUE played a pivotal role in facilitating these exchanges, helping to steer the process and foster deeper collaboration. Additionally, MIP has assumed a leading role in certain transversal working groups and has been integrated into others, further reinforcing cross-CSA collaboration. PREP4BLUE also established a direct and constructive dialogue with MIP, particularly on issues such as identifying suitable business models to support the scale-up of Mission-related solutions. However, a challenge has emerged regarding the visibility and complementarity of the various helpdesks. While the helpdesks established by the CSAs and the one developed by MIP serve different yet complementary functions, they are not always clearly perceived by end-users as distinct services. This creates a risk of tool duplication and reduced visibility for CSA-developed services.

In the area of monitoring and indicators, progress has been more gradual. This is largely due to the diversity of objectives across CSAs, which makes harmonisation of procedures complex. Nonetheless, coordination efforts continue, with PREP4BLUE and partners actively working toward greater alignment.

Several working groups have emerged from these coordination efforts, each focused on key thematic areas:

- Communication Collaborative
- Citizen Engagement Collaborative
- Helpdesk Working Group
- Monitoring, Indicators and KPIs Working Group

Beyond the working groups, additional joint initiatives have included:

- Co-organisation of communication campaigns
- Co-hosting of workshops at major events, such as the European Ocean and Waters Days (March 2025)
- Monthly coordination meetings among CSAs and with MIP
- Joint planning and co-organisation of Pilot Stakeholder Assemblies in each LH area

To avoid stakeholder fatigue and overlap, PREP4BLUE coordinated closely with LH CSAs to align event calendars and engagement efforts. This included seven online coordination meetings and a series of informal one-on-one discussions tailored to each CSA's specific needs. These sessions helped assess the stakeholder engagement goals of each LH CSA and facilitated efficient collaboration.

Co-organisation of the Atlantic (November 2024) and Danube/Black Sea (November 2024) Pilot Stakeholder Assemblies between Prep4Blue (CPMR, CNR & CETMAR), the LH CSAs and their respective IAs have been positively received also.

- A jointly designed workshop on citizen engagement by BlueMissionAA and PREP4BLUE, held at the third Mission Arena of BlueMissionBANOS in Amsterdam (November 2024)

- The co-organisation of the event *“Sustainable Rivers: Bridging Local and European Initiatives”* (21 May 2024, Rome), led by CNR, Rotary Distretto 2080, PREP4BLUE, and BlueMissionMed, with support from the Italian Hub. This pilot event addressed Mission objectives related to river system management and explored ways to scale up local impacts across the Mediterranean and beyond.

Prep4Blue has also been present in several Mission meetings and online workshops with various stakeholders of the Mission Ocean & Waters Ecosystem

2.1.1.1 *Bilateral meetings with (future) Mission Stakeholders by Coordination team*

The consortium also engaged in written exchanges and bilateral meetings to showcase PREP4BLUE’s results and explain the Mission to various organisations. Providing a fully comprehensive list is difficult, as these interactions were numerous and took place both during official events and outside conventional settings—often directly involving individual PREP4BLUE partners. Below is a partial list of interactions conducted specifically by the Coordination Team (Ifremer and EuroMarine): FFESSM – *French Federation of Underwater Sports and Studies* (email exchanges on P4B results in February 2024) : <https://ffessm.fr/>

- Planète Mer (meeting 23 February 2024) : <https://www.planetemer.org/>
- World Ocean Council (meeting 4 March 2024) : <https://www.oceancouncil.org/>
- Foundation Philippe Cousteau (meeting 4 March 2024) : <http://uniondelosoceanos.com/>
- Greenov-ites (meeting 20 March 2025) : <https://greenov.green/>
- Sète Agglopolé Méditerranée (meeting 20 March 2025) : <https://www.agglopolé.fr/>
- Pôle Aquimer (meeting 25 March 2025) : <https://www.poleaquimer.com/>
- Galileo User Services Support (meeting 25 April 2025): <https://www.euspa.europa.eu/eu-space-programme/galileo>

Presentations, done by Coordinator (Ifremer), of Prep4Blue results at (Mission) project events :

- CLIMAREST consortium meeting in Brest, France – 15th April 2024
- PHAROS Kick-off meeting in Tenerife, Spain (online presentation) – 27th September 2024

2.1.1.2 *Collaborative Working Groups*

Several collaborative working groups have been initiated and/or attended by Prep4Blue with other Mission projects and the MIP Ocean:

- **Communication Collaborative (monthly meetings):** to discuss all Communication aspects linked to the Mission with Mission projects, DG MARE, CINEA and MIP Ocean.
To supplement the Communication Strategy and other related tools/resources and ensure their use, Prep4Blue created a Mission Ocean and Waters Communications Working Group. Known as the “Communications Collaborative”, it facilitates information sharing between PREP4BLUE partners, Lighthouse CSAs, the Mission Implementation Platform, EC communications leaders, and other EC Mission-funded project stakeholders to ensure all parties have the necessary and proper information, tools, and assets for communicating Mission Ocean and Waters’ endeavours.
While it was started by Prep4Blue, it is now administered by the MIP to avoid duplicating efforts and because the MIP was tasked with creating a similar platform after Prep4Blue had established this one. While the MIP convenes the gathering, CSA partners take turns leading the monthly meetings, so that it remains an open space for MO stakeholders to exchange and support each other. The network enables us to share information and establish linkages more

easily. Regular engagements with the MIP and EC allow us to stay informed of EC products and utilize hard-to-access resources, such as email lists and databases, without compromising rules and regulations. On average, those monthly meetings host approximately 50 participants, suggesting a positive uptake.

- **Citizen engagement Collaborative:** community of practices on citizen engagement with Mission projects.

As part of the effort to seed a Mission Ocean and Waters citizen engagement Community of Practice, PREP4BLUE organised a meeting with the 4 LH CSAs and the MIP on 14 March 2023. This was a key first step in establishing links between the citizen engagement teams of the Mission-funded projects.

This effort has continued to the point that now almost all 60 projects' engagement teams are networked, co-organise events (e.g., PREP4BLUE's presentation in BLUEMISSIONAA's weekly networking events), cross-promote citizen engagement activities, attend each other's training, and generally grow citizen participation in Mission-related activities.

- **Helpdesk Working Group:** to discuss all Helpdesk aspects linked to the various resources developed by the CSAs and the MIP Ocean for the Mission.

To prevent duplication of efforts, the Helpdesk teams from each Lighthouse Coordination and Support Action (CSA) and the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP) held regular meetings, led by CETMAR as the partner responsible for the Prep4Blue helpdesk. This collaboration facilitated information sharing and streamlined outputs. Resources were exchanged among CSAs; for instance, Prep4Blue incorporated the Q&A developed by BlueMissionBANOS, and BlueMissionAA adopted Prep4Blue's Helpdesk structure. These interactions provided a framework to discuss technical aspects, such as recording support tickets and the necessity for a common Mission glossary. On average, those monthly meetings have close to 6-10 participants.

- **Monitoring, Indicators, KPIs across the Mission CSAs Working group**

In order to avoid duplications of what was already developed in the first two/three years of the Mission, the CSAs (PREP4BLE, BMAA, BMBANOS; BMMED, ECODALLI) meet regularly since 2024 and with MIP since 2025, to exchange on and to harmonise the approaches in the development of Indicators, KPI and Monitoring Frameworks, and to communicate the outputs from the CSAs and MIP among each other, and in the Mission-Context.

Based on these discussions, it was proposed to hold a workshop during the Ocean Days in March 2025 to validate the uptake potential of the developed Indicators, KPIs and Monitoring Frameworks with key stakeholders. A joint, co-creation effort is of value to find complementarities and to fill gaps towards harmonising the monitoring frameworks and indicators across the Lighthouse CSAs, and with MIP and EEA. The workshop outcomes are aimed to be reported in BMB deliverable D5.3.

- **Mission Ocean and Waters Lighthouses Working Group (monthly meetings),** initiated by BlueMissionAA, but taken over by Prep4Blue in 2024. It's a meeting with all the Mission CSAs project Coordinators and their Project Manager(s) and it aims at exchanging the advancements of each other's projects and discuss the evolution of the Mission as well as the links and relationships with MIP Ocean, Mission Secretariat and the Commission.
- **Mission Ocean and Waters LH and MIP Ocean Working Group (monthly meetings).** It's a meeting with all the Mission CSAs project Coordinators and their Project Manager(s) and the MIP Ocean Coordinator and MIP task leader(s). It aims at exchanging the advancements of each other's projects and discussing the evolution of the Mission.

2.1.2 CSAs Legacy document

The constant coordination of the CSAs and exchanges between the CSAs, MIP and the Mission Secretariat has resulted in a CSA Legacy document: *Nys, C., de Liedekerke, V., Schultz-Zehden, A., Klatt, F., Schlichenmaier, N., Conti, E., Li Chen, T., Faria, A., Francocci, F. (2025) Mission Ocean & Waters: Cross-basin Lessons and Insights from CSAs (Version 1.0). PREP4BLUE, BlueMissionAA, EcoDaLLi, BlueMissionMed, BlueMissionBANOS. <https://doi.org/10.13155/105135>*

This report presents the implementation methods of each Mission Ocean and Waters LightHouse CSA ([BlueMissionBANOS](#), [BlueMissionAA](#), [BlueMissionMed](#), [EcoDaLLi](#)) within their respective areas and the implementation of the overarching CSA ([Prep4Blue](#)). It also highlights the role of these CSAs in connecting Mission-funded projects and enhancing synergies, and highlights some of their key activities.

Throughout the report, the position and interactions of each CSA within the Mission project ecosystem were explored, as well as their collaboration with the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP Ocean) and the Mission Secretariat.

Another section focused on the results achieved by each CSA, particularly those that will be transferred as a legacy to the broader Mission ecosystem.

The Legacy document also addressed the barriers and challenges faced by the CSAs, along with their recommendations. Finally, there was a short discussion on how the LH CSAs envision their role in the second phase of the Mission (2026-2030), offering key recommendations and suggested actions for improvement.

This first version of the Legacy document has been widely shared since the 7th of March 2025. A second version, under the lead of one of the LH CSAs, is planned for the second half of 2025 or the beginning of 2026. This will allow the LH CSAs to update it with their end results and final recommendations expected at the end of each respective project. Prep4Blue will also update several sections on Prep4Blue, but also the more transversal topics.

2.1.3 Mission Core Network & Other Missions

Engagement with Mission Core Network (TRAMI¹⁴ project) was ensured as Prep4Blue was a member of the TRAMI Sounding Board. The TRAMI project was there to foster synergies and best practice exchange between the five missions with regard to governance models. It now, since project has ended, a life on its own. During these meetings several exchanges happened between Prep4Blue (Mission Ocean and Waters representative) and the other Mission representatives.

Another exchange between Missions happened at the French national level during the French National Cross-Missions Meetings (ComOp Recherche – GT Missions) that started in the second trimester of 2024 and happened on average every month.

These represents 3 synergy meetings (category “Other Missions” in Table 2) of Prep4Blue’s Coordination team between December 2023 and April 2025.

¹⁴ **TRAMI**: National Core Network for all Missions, coherence and alignment of programs and resources (<https://www.trami5missions.eu/>)

2.2 Creation of synergies with European initiatives and organisations (Task 1.3)

Task 1.3 (T1.3) was modified through an amendment in August 2023, with a focus shift towards identifying and engaging relevant stakeholders through the Mission Charter. More specifically, T1.3 identified relevant initiatives and organisations with potential for collaboration and for becoming part of the Mission development, *e.g.*, by cross-referencing contributors to the UN Ocean Decade with actions already submitted to the Charter, with a particular focus on making links between Ocean and Water actors for R&I.

After delivering a communication campaign promoting the Mission Charter and support material for Charter contributors in RP1, Prep4Blue has focused its efforts on elaborating guidance and best practice examples of National Mission Hubs to help countries improve or set up their own national hubs. Existing hubs have been contacted to share their experiences and useful resources, and some examples are featured in the guidance as best practices. The guidance document is accessible through Prep4Blue's website: prep4blue.eu/portfolio/guidance-for-establishing-mission-ocean-and-waters-national-hubs and was disseminated through Prep4Blue social media in April 2025.

Prep4Blue is also a member the EU4Ocean coalition and has participated to their meetings. Prep4Blue also is a member of the MPA Europe stakeholder network¹⁵ and has links, through WP3, with the European Solidarity Corps.

2.3 Contribution to the EU Agenda for International Ocean Governance, focusing on the UN Decade on Ocean Science for Sustainable Development and the UN Decade of Ecological Restoration (2021-2030) (Task 1.4)

In 2024, the European Commission and the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC-UNESCO) adopted a joint roadmap to strengthen alignment between the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (Ocean Decade) and EU-led initiatives. These initiatives include the Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters (MO), the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership, and the All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance. This roadmap marks a significant step toward fostering synergy across global and European marine science and policy frameworks.

As part of this effort, PREP4BLUE developed a dedicated database to support the visibility and implementation of this joint roadmap. The tool highlights projects and events that are contributing simultaneously to both the Ocean Decade and Mission Ocean objectives. To date, out of the 940 signatories of the Mission Ocean Charter, more than 200 projects and events, spanning various geographic scales, have also been endorsed by the UN Ocean Decade (*Source Date: [WaveLinks/Projects](#) – Visited February 2025*). Notably, EU-funded projects such as the CSA BlueMissionAA, the Blue Economy Baltic Forum, and the CLIMAREST project have expanded their global reach and impact through Ocean Decade endorsement.

PREP4BLUE partners are actively involved in the implementation of the UN Ocean Decade, contributing expertise and leadership across multiple initiatives:

- JPI Oceans acts as the UN Ocean Decade's *implementing partner for Europe*.

¹⁵ MPA Europe stakeholder network: <https://mpa-europe.eu/stakeholder-network/>

- KDM co-organised the first Ocean Decade Kick-off Conference (virtual, 2021) and hosted V.ECOP Days 2024 in Barcelona.
- CSIC co-organised the second UN Ocean Decade Conference held in Barcelona (April 2024).
- VLIZ hosts the Secretariat of the National Decade Committee (NDC) for Belgium and Flanders. On 25 April 2024, VLIZ and the Flemish UNESCO Commission (VUC) co-organised the event *"Ocean Decade Meets Mission Ocean: Blue Skills for a Sustainable Economy"* in Ostend. Held under the auspices of the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the EU, the event brought together academia, policymakers, industry leaders, and civil society to collaborate on blue skills development.
- CSIC also supports the Ocean Cities Network (OC-NET), a UN Decade programme.
- Ifremer leads the UN Decade Programme *"One Deep Ocean Network."*

In addition, the TransOcean working group—supported by EuroMarine and involving key partners such as CSIC, IFREMER, SDU, HCMR, UNiBO, UNIPD, CCMAR, MARE, SZN, IZO, IRD, MaREI and others—plays a crucial role in bridging European and global efforts. This group fosters networking and joint activities to support transoceanic, transversal, and transformative programmes. Its core members have co-authored a paper exploring the synergies between the Mission and the Ocean Decade in advancing citizen engagement (*"Collaborative bottom-up Trust Missions: A long-term strategy with and for people and Nature"*, under review with *Nature Portfolio Journal*, 2025).

PREP4BLUE partners have also actively promoted the Mission through international platforms and events, including the Ocean Decade online communication forum and major global conferences. A key moment was the 2nd UN Ocean Decade Conference (April 2024, Barcelona), where PREP4BLUE co-organised four official satellite events focusing on citizen engagement. These included:

- *"Enbluement: Connecting science and arts to expand our belonging to the Ocean"* (ID#255/256), for which a video was produced to capture the event's atmosphere and messages.
- *"Empowering science, policy and society through co-design for sustainable ocean development"* (ID#250), which highlighted participatory approaches in support of the Mission.
- *"Diving from local to global ocean literacy: Exploring, sharing and developing successful practices to know, feel and join the living ocean"*,
- *"Cities with the Ocean – Ocean science for the sustainable development of coastal cities and ports"*

Representatives from the consortium - namely VLIZ (Flanders Marine institute), CNR, Ifremer and JPI Ocean - are very active in the UN Ocean Decade initiatives at strategic and operational levels. They are involved as core members of Decade National Committees (e.g., CNR is hosting and coordinating the Italian National Committee); as contributors to Decade Collaborative Office (e.g., VLIZ / DCO Data Sharing Strategy Implementation Group) and Decade Collaborative Centres (e.g., Ifremer / DCC Ocean Observation); or are endorsed as Decade Implementing Partners (JPI, VLIZ). Partners also lead Decade-endorsed Programs (e.g., CNR/CoastPredict; Ifremer/OneDeepOcean), Projects and Contributions (e.g., Ifremer/French Priority Research Program "Ocean & Climate, an ocean of solutions). VLIZ holds the secretariat of the National Ocean Decade Committee NDC for Belgium. CSIC is a co-organiser of the UN Ocean Decade Conference in Barcelona, April, 2024. Ifremer is the co-organiser of the One Ocean Science Congress, which takes place just before the Third UN Ocean Decade Conference in June 2025 in Nice, France.

3 Conclusions

At the end of the project, it can be concluded that Prep4Blue has been involved and contributed to co-shaping key activities of the Mission “Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030.” The project also spread the word about the Mission at the European and international levels.

Through its role as a linking agent and implementing project of the Mission with the other LH CSAs, Prep4Blue has been present in all Mission-related major events and online workshops, either online /or in-person. These events allowed Prep4Blue to meet and build links with partners of other projects involved in the Mission, create synergies within the Mission Ecosystem, etc. For some of the major European instances, some partners have been involved in the organisation, which allowed them to build links directly with some of the “local” stakeholders. Prep4Blue has also been heavily involved in presenting a unified communication, through various channels, about the Mission to the various “Ocean and Waters” stakeholders to boost the outreach of the Mission Charter and encourage the setting up of National Mission Hubs.

While slow building in the beginning, lots of synergies have been implemented in the whole Mission Ocean & Waters Ecosystem. Prep4Blue has ensured a good collaboration with the Mission governance and has strived to align the expectations and efforts of all the LH CSAs, and through them the LH (R)IAs, with the MIP Ocean and Mission Secretariat (as representatives of the European Commission).

At the international level, Prep4Blue is involved in the UN Ocean Decade, mainly in the UN Ocean Decade initiatives at strategic and operational levels. One of the partners was also the co-organiser of the UN Ocean Decade conference in Barcelona in 2024. Partners are also involved in organising the next UN conference on the Ocean in 2025. These high-level events highlight the importance of the Ocean and help to bring forward Prep4Blue’s work at the international level.